
WHAT TO READ NEXT? AN INTERACTIVE VISUALIZATION TOOL FOR EXPLORATORY LITERATURE REVIEW

TECHNICAL REPORT *

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ABSTRACT

This report presents a web-based tool that supports a research workflow by helping them explore a set of papers and decide what to read next. It uses interactive visualization for exploratory analysis of citation relationships, including co-citation and bibliographic coupling, and shows citation flow with a Sankey view. The interface links multiple views so users can filter links, compare different relationship types, and inspect paper attributes like year, field, and impact while exploring the network. It also provides simple recommendations by ranking unread papers based on how strongly they connect to papers the user has already read. The report demonstrates the tool on a small dataset collected from OpenAlex API.

1 Introduction

Bibliometric mapping tools are great at giving an overview of a field by turning many papers into a map that highlights clusters and connections. For example, VOSviewer is designed to construct and view large bibliometric maps, including co-citation (van Eck and Waltman [2010]), and CiteSpace visualizes co-citation networks to show major clusters and emerging trends over time (Chen [2006]). But when you are doing a literature review, the hard part is often more micro and practical. It is about keeping paper attributes like year, impact, and field visible while exploring the network, comparing different relationship types side by side like co-citation versus bibliographic coupling, and turning what you see into a concrete reading plan. This project addresses that gap by linking multiple views (co-citation, bibliographic coupling, and a citation-flow Sankey), letting users smoothly switch between an attribute-based scatterplot and a force-directed network layout, and adding interactive recommendations that highlight which unread papers are most connected to what the user has already read.

Prior work in visual analytics of scientific literature has shown the value of interactive sensemaking in complex networks. GraphDice supports exploratory analysis of multivariate networks through interactive, direct-manipulation views so analysts can iteratively compare structure alongside attributes (Bezerianos et al. [2010]). In dynamic-network settings, GraphDiaries demonstrates how temporal navigation and change-aware transitions can help users understand evolving network structure (Bach et al. [2013]). Beyond exploration, van den Elzen and van Wijk propose moving from detail to overview via selections and aggregations (DOSA), where users build “selections of interest” through interactions and the system automatically produces an aggregated overview for network detail and high-level summaries (Van den Elzen and Van Wijk [2014]). Complementing these visualization-centric systems, researchers have also developed methods to interpret co-citation clusters by combining structural clustering with semantic cues such as automatic labeling and summarization to improve interpretability of cluster meanings (Chen et al. [2010]).

This tool is inspired by GraphDice, which demonstrate that putting data on a scatterplot helps people see patterns from different angles that they would miss in a regular network map. (Bezerianos et al. [2010]). In this project, the visualization tool focuses on sense-making for users’ own collection of papers by modeling relationships between papers. It does so by using co-citation and bibliometric coupling. A co-citation network connects two papers when

*Code and data available at: <https://arsalan-fard.github.io/Co-Citation-Visualization/>

they are cited together by another paper. It reveals how later work perceives them as related. A bibliographic coupling network connects two papers when they cite some of the same references. It captures topical similarity from the authors’ perspective at publication time. In addition, a Sankey view supports citation-flow exploration by visualizing how selected papers connect to their referenced works and citing papers.

While the scatterplot assigns each paper a fixed position based on the selected x-axis and y-axis attributes, I also include a stability control that interpolates between an attribute-driven layout and a force-directed layout. At one end, papers remain at their axis positions for direct comparison of metadata patterns. At the other, the network forces strongly connected papers closer and pushing weakly related ones apart to emphasize co-citation or coupling structure. This makes it possible to smoothly transit between “attribute similarity” and “network similarity” views without losing context. In addition, an edge-strength threshold filter is provided to remove weak links.

2 Dataset

2.1 Data Acquisition

The dataset consists of 59 papers collected for my master’s project on public participatory design. Since I have already read a subset of these papers, the goal is to reveal how they relate to each other and to prioritize which papers to read next based on citations and shared references.

To build the dataset, I used the OpenAlex API and feed it list of DOIs to collect all citing and cited papers by our focal papers. After retrieving the incoming and outgoing citations for each paper, the we can construct a co-citation edge list and a bibliographic coupling edge list. In these lists, the weight between two papers represents the number of distinct external papers that cite both (or that both cite). Finally, a ‘read status’ was manually added to indicate which papers I have already read.

2.2 Attributes

Table 1 presents the attributes collected from OpenAlex. While most features are simply paper metadata, some are provided heuristically by OpenAlex. For instance, the Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI) is intended to reflect how a paper’s citation performance compares to expectations for similar publications (e.g., same field and year).

Additionally, OpenAlex assigns each work a topical hierarchy. In our dataset, `domain` denotes a broad discipline, `field` represents a more specific area, and `subfield` captures fine-grained research topics. We use these three categorical attributes as axes to identify topical clusters and show how these clusters are related. The `field` attribute is also used in the Sankey view to show where papers draw their references from and where they have citation impact.

In addition to these attributes, table 2 lists the attributes computed specifically for this study.

Attribute	Type	How it is used
<code>publication_date</code>	temporal	Axis option (time) that supports temporal comparisons papers.
<code>cited_by_count</code>	quantitative	Axis option and also size of nodes.
<code>fwci</code>	quantitative	Axis option
<code>domain</code>	categorical	Axis option to compare broad areas and detect cross-domain bridges.
<code>field</code>	categorical	Axis option. Also used in Sankey as an aggregation key.
<code>field (citations)</code>	categorical	Audience-side category in the Sankey diagram.
<code>field (references)</code>	categorical	Foundation-side category in the Sankey diagram.
<code>subfield</code>	categorical	Axis option for finer-grained topical grouping.
<code>read</code>	boolean	Marks papers already read.
<code>type</code>	boolean	Heuristic “survey/review” flag from OpenAlex for optional highlighting/filtering.
<code>citing_paper_publication_date</code>	temporal	Used to build per-paper citation-time summaries (e.g., bursts/recency cues) for time-aware context.
<code>paper1,paper2,cocitation_strength</code>	quantitative	Defines the co-citation graph. weight controls edge filtering and weighted-degree computations.
<code>paper1,paper2,coupling_strength</code>	quantitative	Defines the bibliographic coupling graph. weight controls edge filtering and weighted-degree computations.

Table 1: Attributes used in the project.

Attribute	Type	How it is computed
degree (centrality)	quantitative (int)	Number of edges in the currently displayed network (after applying the edge-strength threshold).
weightedDegree	quantitative (float)	Sum of edge weights (co-citation strength or coupling strength) in the currently displayed network.
betweenness	quantitative (float)	Betweenness centrality computed on the currently displayed graph with Brandes algorithm. set to 0 in fallback cases.
recommendation score	quantitative (float)	For each unread paper, summed adjacency weight to all neighbors under the selected mode (co-citation, coupling, or both). used to rank recommendations.

Table 2: Derived (computed) attributes.

3 Visualization

The project consists of three main visualizations. A co-citation network, a bibliographic coupling network, and a Sankey diagram. And two side visualizations complement these. One is a recommendation heatmap that ranks and visualizes candidate unread papers by their aggregated connection strength to the user’s read set. And second is radial treemap that organizes the corpus by domain, field, subfield. It provides a quick overview of topical coverages.

In this section, we explore different combinations of attributes as axes for scatterplot, thresholds, stability, and view modes to show what each visualization reveals.

3.1 Features Description

Before mentioning the insights provided by each graph, it is essential to understand the functional features of the interface. As illustrated in Figure 1, the left panel contains the visualization controls. At the top left, users can select up to two of the three available visualization graphs. The Edge Strength Threshold sliders allow for filtering papers based on minimum of co-citation or bibliographic coupling strength.

The Stability slider determines the influence of edge-based forces on node positioning. At a stability value of 1, nodes are fixed to the exact positions defined by their X and Y axes. Conversely, at a value of 0, the graph is shaped entirely by force-directed simulation, where strong co-citation relationships pull nodes together while repelling others. Adjusting the slider between 0 and 1 allows users to observe the interplay between fixed attributes and the network structure.

Finally, the Node Color checkboxes used for visual categorization. Read papers are highlighted in green, and surveys or reviews appear in purple. Additionally, selecting the Burst option visualizes the temporal distribution and intensity of a paper’s citations directly within the node. Edge colors and width represent the strength of relationship between nodes. The color map is the same for heatmap and burst to make it easy to understand.

Figure 1: Overview of visualization.

About selection, users can select one or multiple nodes directly in the network views. Once a selection is made, non-selected nodes and links are dimmed to keep attention on the chosen papers. Selections have influence across the interface. For example, in Figure 1, selecting a paper in the graph immediately highlights the same paper in the Sankey diagram and updates the recommendation heatmap. Group selection is also supported through the radial treemap. Clicking a domain, field, or subfield selects all papers in that category (Figure 2). This helps users to quickly explore a subset. Clicking on empty space clears the current selection.

For dense regions where multiple nodes overlap, users can hold Ctrl and drag to zoom in/out. Finally, the bottom corner arrow buttons allow collapsing the left or right side panels. It expands the central workspace when more room is needed for the main visualizations.

Figure 2: Selecting Physical Science domain in the treemap to highlight multiple papers.

3.2 Scatter Plot (Stability = 1)

When stability is set to 1.0, node positions are determined entirely by the selected x and y axis metrics, so the network behaves like a scatter plot. In this mode, switching between the co-citation and bibliographic-coupling views does not change the node positions, but it does change the displayed links and any connectivity-derived encodings (e.g., degree-based node size). Because the number of possible axis pairings is large, I only mention a small set of combinations that were informative for the dataset.

3.2.1 Citation vs. Publication Date

Placing publication date on the x-axis and citation count on the y-axis reveals an expected pattern. Older papers have had more time to gather citations and the scatterplot shows an overall downward trend (Figure 3). This view also summarizes citation distribution across years and makes outliers easy to identify. While we do not have an outlier here, the highlighted paper (hovered with white outer ring) in Figure 3 is showing a mix between being recent and having high citation. Its domain/field context can be seen in the paper hierarchy view. Also, hovering over the node reveals dense co-citation connections. It shows that it is not only well-cited but also has relatively good co-citation or establishment in the local knowledge. Since counting links directly is difficult in dense regions, we can map node size to degree so that highly connected papers are immediately distinguishable.

3.2.2 Citation/FWCI

Because raw citation counts highly differ across disciplines, it's misleading to analyze based solely on citation. Therefore, we instead place FWCI on the x-axis and citation count on the y-axis (Figure 4). In this view, disagreement appears where the two measures diverge. Papers in the top-left have high citation counts but comparatively low FWCI which means while the paper is popular, it is not outperforming field expectations, whereas papers in the bottom-right have high FWCI despite low raw citations. In our dataset, many papers fall in the bottom-right region, including the selected example. It indicates a paper that is impactful relative to its discipline even if citations remain modest. The

Figure 3: Citation/Date illustration.

selection also highlights the corresponding subfield in the paper hierarchy or radial treemap (*Geography, Planning and Development*) and reports read coverage (23% of the papers in that subfield have been read). In addition, the recommendation heatmap ranks this paper among the top suggestions, showing that it is strongly connected to the current reading set. Together, these signals suggest the paper is worth prioritizing. Because it is highly relevant to the user’s interests and performs well in its field, even though it is not among the most-cited items overall.

Figure 4: Citation/FWCI illustration.

3.2.3 Co-Citation/Betweenness

Figure 5 illustrates plotting co-citation strength against betweenness centrality which are two complementary roles in the network. Papers in the bottom-right (high co-citation, low betweenness) act as within-theme canonical works that repeatedly used together inside a specific community. And papers in the top-left (high betweenness, lower co-citation) act as bridges that connect distinct themes, even if they are not the strongest hubs within any single cluster. The purple (survey) paper positioned between these extremes exemplifies a mixed role. The Sankey diagram provides additional context by summarizing each selected paper’s disciplinary *foundations* (fields it cites, left side) and *audience* (fields that cite it, right side). For example, the green paper shows concentration in a small number of fields as audience

(e.g., Social Sciences and Environmental Science), while the blue paper exhibits a more evenly distributed audience across multiple fields. This contrast suggests different reading priorities. Hub-like papers like the green paper are strong anchors within a theme, while strongly cited bridge papers may be preferable when the goal is cross-disciplinary coverage.

Figure 5: Co-Citation/Betweenness illustration.

3.3 Network of Cocitation and Bibliographic Coupling (Stability = 0)

In this setup, we examine relationship between papers through two complementary lenses. Co-citation shows how the community uses papers together, while bibliographic coupling shows how authors cite other papers together. For instance, in Figure 6, central nodes in the co-citation network tend to be well-established works. On the other hand, central nodes in the bibliographic coupling network provide an immediate indication of active topics that may become central in the co-citation network in the future. If a cluster remains similar in both views, it likely represents a topic with shared foundations and shared usage.

The color gradient on each node shows the temporal distribution of citations. The center corresponds to the publication time, and the outer ring corresponds to more recent years. Therefore, nodes with stronger color toward the edge and a lighter center indicate fast-growing attention.

Finally, because the dataset is relatively small and topic-focused, many papers share similar references and are co-cited together, so communities do not separate cleanly. Therefore, there is another dataset provided in the Figure 7 to demonstrate that the system can reveal meaningful structure when enough papers are available. It illustrates a sample of 200 randomly selected CHI papers and their co-citation network.

In this larger corpus, the force-directed layout produces clearer community structure. Papers that are frequently co-cited are pulled closer together, forming visually separable clusters that reflect sub-areas within CHI, while more interdisciplinary papers appear between clusters as bridges. The analytics sidebar complements the network by summarizing topical coverage through the domain–field–subfield hierarchy and by enabling recommendation views. But the key observation in this figure is that increasing the number and diversity of papers makes clustering emerge more distinctly.

However, because the layout involves both pulling and pushing forces, we can obtain more distinguishable clusters by setting stability to a value between 0 and 1, which provides a fixed reference while still allowing the network to self-organize. This is shown in the next section.

3.4 Network of Co-citation and Field Distribution (Stability = 0.80)

In this example, we map both the x and y axis to each paper’s field, creating a field-by-field view. It makes cross-field co-citation links easy to spot (Figure 8 left). We then set the stability parameter to 0.96 in the co-citation network. It produces a hybrid layout that remains largely constrained by the field axes while still allowing the co-citation force

Figure 6: Network of Cocitation and Bibliographic Coupling illustration.

Figure 7: Network of Cocitation for 200 Random CHI Papers illustration.

model to gently adjust positions (Figure 8 right). As a result, papers that are frequently co-cited comes closer together and weakly related papers separate. This can reveal bridging papers and stronger connections between fields. As we can see, the selected papers between environmental science and social science are also recommended by heatmap. Because they are the same nodes in the previous network where the stability was 0.

4 Technical Details

This project is a browser-based application built with vanilla HTML/CSS/JavaScript and D3.js, organized into lightweight modules for shared state, UI controls, network rendering, Sankey rendering, and an analytics sidebar. The same network visualizer is reused for both co-citation and bibliographic-coupling views. It loads CSV data, enriches nodes with metadata and computed graph metrics (e.g., degree, weighted degree, and betweenness), and positions nodes using a combination of axis constraints and force simulation.

A stability parameter blends axis forces with physical forces using a quadratic ease-out function ($\text{weight} = 1 - (1 - \text{stability})^2$). This non-linear mapping provides finer control near high stability values (0.9–1.0). It allows us to slightly move the nodes from their position. Additionally, transitions between graph states do not redraw the graph, allowing

Figure 8: Network of Co-citation and Field Distribution Illustration

users to move smoothly from an axis-based scatterplot to a topology-driven network layout. I also interpolate link positions so edges do not snap ahead of moving nodes.

5 Limitations and Future Works

For future work, the system can better support exploration by providing interaction history, so that when users switch between axis setups and views, previous selections and parameter should be recovered.

Selection can be improved with richer interactions such as lasso selection, and set operations (union/intersection) to compare groups across co-citation and coupling networks.

Clustering can be made more explicit by integrating community-detection methods and clearer visual labeling of groups. And we can add quality indicators to avoid over-interpreting weak structure in small dataset.

Temporal filtering would also be helpful. It enables users to focus on specific periods and observe how the network, bursts, and cross-field flows evolve over time.

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